

National Open Research Forum Policy Brief Series

National Open Access Monitoring - Appendices

Developed by the NORF subgroup on OA Monitoring, drawing on previous work carried out by the IUA Librarians' Group (IUALG) Rian Technical Working Group and the National Open Research Forum. Dec 2021

Success Criteria

What indicators would suggest that OA monitoring is doing its job & is a valued, used and successful service?

#	KPI	Measure	Importance
1	Usage by Irish Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) to measure funded research outputs	Reports produced by RPOs/RFOs and figures fed into national reports are based on OA Monitoring data	Must have
2	Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to measure OA	Reports produced by RPOs/RFOs and figures fed into national reports are based on OA Monitoring data, e.g. the “% of publications deposited in Open Access repositories” KPI in the 2018-2020 Higher Education System Performance Framework	Must have
3	Usage by Irish RPOs/RFOs to promote/enable OA compliance	Public documentation detailing how OA Monitoring is used to verify RPO/RFO OA policy, with corresponding instructions for their funded researchers	Must have

4	Usage by Irish national consortia to inform new OA publishing agreements, and monitor existing agreements	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data	
5	Usage by government departments to measure and report on OA compliance as overall % of Irish research publications	Reports produced by Government Departments (e.g. DBEI, Education) and figures fed into E.U. reports are based on OA Monitoring data	Must have
6	Demonstrable engagement by researchers in using OA Monitoring when assessing their OA compliance	Documentation on RFO websites guiding researchers to OA Monitoring for assessment/evidence of OA compliance	Must have
7	Demonstrable use of OA Monitoring to inform and support strategic developments in the area of Open Science	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data or statistics in national reports or working groups, e.g. NORF or equivalent	Must have
8	Usage by publishers to monitor visibility of published content and analyse sectoral performance relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies	OA Monitoring cited as source of data	
9	Usage of portal interface	Web and/or COUNTER statistics indicating user engagement with the service	Must have
10	Integration of OA Monitoring data into RFO or RPO systems through API etc.	E.g. documented examples/case-studies of direct integration with RFO grant management systems or processes, RPO CRIS systems or process, RPO Institutional Repository systems, other Irish repositories, or processes	Should have

11	Integration of OA Monitoring data into external systems	OA Monitoring cited as a source of data.	Could have
12	Active, ongoing engagement among stakeholders	This is a rapidly evolving area, with new datasets and services becoming available every year. A key indicator of the success of OA Monitoring will be the extent to which stakeholders are engaged and the system is responsive to improvement and critical evaluation through successive, continuous iterations. In addition to more formal feedback from broader stakeholders, the Repository Manager constituency is an important stakeholder in this regard	Must have

User Personas

Id	Persona/Role	Description	Motivation	Frequency of Use
A	Policy strategist/analyst	This user works in one of the Irish RFOs, national consortia, or government departments.	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with national-level statistics and monitoring of research outputs and open access in order to inform strategic direction in relation to funding, impact assessment, publisher negotiations, transformative agreement monitoring, and Open Science/Access	Medium (Biannual reporting, reasonably regular checks on performance or on-demand querying)

B	Research support officer/analyst	This user works in the research support service or library of an Irish RPO	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring national-level visibility of institutional research and in analysing their institution's OA performance relative to peer institutions, and in establishing compliance with RFO policies	Medium (reasonably regular checks on performance, e.g. once every month or so)
C	Repository Manager	This user is responsible for managing a publications repository at one of the Irish RPOs	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring OA publications from their system are accurately reflected.	Medium (reasonably regular checks on performance, e.g. once every month or so)
D	Individual researcher	This user is a researcher working at an Irish RPO	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) establishing whether their publications are in compliance with the policies of their RFOs and RPO; b) ensuring their research outputs are visible at a national level;	Low (On-demand querying prompted, for example, by funding reporting or quality review process) Low individual usage but lots of individuals
E	Publishers	Publishers, aggregators and	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with ensuring visibility of published content and in analysing sectoral performance	Low

		related service providers	relative to peers and compliance with RFO policies	
F	OA Monitoring technical support/contact	This user has been assigned as technical support contact under the OA Monitoring governance structure	In using OA Monitoring, they are primarily concerned with a) ensuring the system is working as expected through monitoring tools etc.; b) being able to easily answer queries and complaints identified by other users	High
G	External integrations	This is a third-party organisation or system	In using OA Monitoring, they are interested in harvesting records or subsets of records for inclusion in another resource or infrastructure	High

User Stories (Functional Requirements and Prioritisation)

Brief descriptions of specific interactions with the service, detailing the relevant personas and the features they require to get their task done

#	Title	User Story	Personas	Importance	Category
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1	Identify % of current OA availability	As an analyst, I want to be able to easily identify the % of Irish peer-reviewed publications that are Open Access	A,B,C	Must have	Reports
2	Identify OA progress over time	As an analyst, I want to be able to compare the % of OA publications against historical 6 month or yearly snapshots to gauge progress towards OA (to gauge progress over time, you can't simply look at OA availability by year of publication)	A,B,C	Must have	Reports
3	Predefined/Dashboard metrics	As a policy strategist/analyst/repository manager/member of the public, I want to be presented with a visual dashboard of the most common statistics, including a) overall record count; b) overall Green/Gold/Closed Open Access breakdown; c) Green/Gold/Closed Open Access breakdown by year; d) overall breakdown by publication type; e) overall and OA breakdown by funder; f) overall and OA breakdown by institution; overall and OA breakdown by publisher	A, B, C, E	Should have	Reports

4	Faceted analysis drill-down functionality	As an analyst/ policy strategist/ researcher, I want to be able to easily visualise the OA % for publications by a number of facets including funding agency, Irish HEI, corresponding author affiliation, by year of publication, by a given subject or keyword, by publisher, by grant award ID, or an arbitrary combinations of these.	A,B,C,D	Must have	Functionality
5	Evaluate performance of different OA strategies	As a policy strategist, I want to be able to compare the relative performance of different approaches to OA (i.e. Green -vs- Gold) and of different OA hubs (i.e. Institutional repositories -vs- preprint servers -vs- open research platforms) to better inform decisions	A,B	Should have	Reports
6	Export OA classification for further analysis	As an analyst, I want to be able to export item-level OA classification data (DOI, Title, OA Classification) for further analysis, either the entire data-set or for specific search results/filters (funder/institution/year/keyword, corresponding author affiliation/publisher/publication type etc.)	A,B,C,D	Should have	Data

7	Compare custom publication set	As an analyst/repository manager/researcher, I want to be able to upload a list of DOIs and have the system return a report indicating a) whether the DOI is in OA Monitoring; b) the OA classification assigned by OA Monitoring	A,B,C,D	Nice to have	Data
8	Grant reporting and assessment	As an analyst/ policy strategist, I want to be able to co-locate publications that have been funded by grants via my organisation/ agency/ department, for reporting.	A,B	Nice to have	Report
9	API Integration	As an analyst/ policy strategist, I want to easily extract data from OA Monitoring regarding material that's been uploaded in OA repositories for incorporation in my organisation's/ department local system, preferably via an API.	A,B	Should have	Data
10	Bibliometric indicators	As a repository support officer/ analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I would like to see bibliometric indicators (e.g., Altmetric, Plum analytics, etc.) when searching for material.	D	Could have	Functionality

11	Standardised usage statistics	As a repository manager, I would like to be able to easily see standardised local usage statistics for material accessed and downloaded from my repository via OA Monitoring.	B,C	Could have	Report
12	Standardised COUNTER compliant statistics	As a repository manager I would like to be able to see COUNTER compliant usage statistics for activities like searches and click-throughs.	B,C	Could have	Report
13	Author disambiguation	As an analyst/ repository manager/ researcher, I want to see all publications by specific authors regardless of variant name forms and affiliation.	A,B,C,D, E	Should have	Functionality
14	Uptime monitoring/alerting	As the technical contact, I want to be alerted when the system is unavailable and be able to review availability of the system over time	F	Must have	Operational
15	Harvest metadata via OAI-PMH	As a downstream aggregator, I want to be able to harvest metadata records or filtered	G	Could have	Functionality

		record sets from OA Monitoring for inclusion in my resource			
16	Documentation	As any user of the system, I want to be able to find succinct but complete documentation regarding: a) what records are contained; b) the criteria for selecting these records; c) the sources from which the records were derived; d) the criteria for open access classification; e) the method of open access classification; f) the governance and history of the system	A,B,C,D, E, F, G	Must have	Documentation
17	Transparent feedback loop regarding functionality	As a user of the system, I want to be able to report an issue with a technical aspect of the system and receive a response in a reasonable period of time in a way that other users can see, e.g. public issue tracker or mailing list	A,B,C,D, E,G	Must have	Operational
18	Transparent feedback loop regarding data	As a user of the system, I want to be able to query or report an issue with the data displayed in the system and receive a response in a reasonable period of time in a way that other users can see, e.g. public issue tracker or mailing list	A,B,C,D, E,G	Must have	Operational

19	Sync with ORCID	As an Irish researcher, I want to be able to sync all works listed in my ORCID profile with an OA monitoring system, ensuring they are indexed and available in the system and as a means of having control over how my work is represented in the national portal	D	Could have	Functionality
20	Periodic data dumps	As an analyst/repository manager/researcher, and in absence of an API or other UI features which allow dynamic access to underlying data, I want to be able to access periodic data dumps/snapshots of included records and their OA classification for further offline analysis, e.g. one every 6 months	A,B,C,D	Should have	Data
21	System status page	As an end-user of the system, I want to be able to access a page which displays the current availability of the system as well as history of system availability over the previous month or year, e.g. https://status.bitbucket.org/ or https://status.github.com	A,B,C,D, E,F,G	Could have	Operational

22	Embargoed access	As an analyst/repository manager/aggregator, I would like to be able to see the % of closed access records which have been deposited in a repository but which are currently embargoed	A,B,C,G	Should have	Data
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